

Supplementary Material

The biodiversity of plant-frugivore interactions: types, functions, and consequences

Pedro Jordano^{1,2}

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¹ Integrative Ecology Group, Estación Biológica de Doñana, CSIC, Avda. Americo Vespucio 26, E-41092 Sevilla, Spain.

² Dept. Biología Vegetal y Ecología, Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, Spain.
Suppl. Material: datasets (both raw and summarized) and code used in any analyses.

Support repository in GitHub.

[\(https://github.com/pedroj/oikos_2026_si_frugivory/\)](https://github.com/pedroj/oikos_2026_si_frugivory/)

Corresponding author: Pedro Jordano. Integrative Ecology Group, Estación Biológica de Doñana, CSIC, Avda. Americo Vespucio 26, E-41092 Sevilla, Spain. Email address: jordano@ebd.csic.es

Prunus mahaleb and *Euterpe edulis* data

Prunus mahaleb (Rosaceae) is a shrub or small tree native to the Mediterranean region. It is a keystone species in the Mediterranean forest, where it is dependent on birds for seed dispersal. The species has been introduced to North America and South America, where it is cultivated for its edible fruits and seeds. Data for the species (frugivory and seed dispersal) come from [Jordano \(1995\)](#); [Jordano and Schupp \(2000\)](#). Information on pollinators was obtained from [\(Jordano, 1993b\)](#). The tree is gynodioecious, with both female and hermaphroditic individual plants. Flowers are visited by a diversified assemblage of bees and flies totaling more than 40 species. Flies are more frequent visitors to male-sterile trees than bees. Herbivory was assessed for each tree by visual censuses and counts of damaged branches and leaves. For each tree, 3-5 different areas (0.5 x 0.5 m) of the canopy at different heights were scanned and the number of twigs and branches with ungulate marks was counted. Due to the fact that these teeth marks cannot be reliably assigned to species, the overall damage attributable to vertebrate herbivores was pooled in a single category. In addition, leaves were inspected for fungi presence, with visual identification, when possible, of the taxa involved based on damage type, form and shape, coloration, etc. A relative damage score was assigned (0-5 ranging from absence through sporadic, frequent, common, and extreme damage) based on counts. Herbivorous insects were censused visually at each tree during the herbivory scans and a relative damage score was also assigned (0-5 ranging from absence through sporadic, frequent, common, and extreme damage) based on counts. Herbivory surveys were carried out from the initial leafing stages until leaves were expanded at full size. This period encompassed the flowering period and extended 2-3 weeks after flowering. Regarding the seed dispersal stage, 38 bird species visit the tree and consume

fruits, eventually dispersing seeds, including thrushes (*Turdus* spp.), robin and redstarts (*Phoenicurus ochruros*, *Erithacus rubecula*), and several species of finches (*Fringilla* spp.) and parids *Parus*, *Cyanistes* spp. feed on pulp and sporadically disperse seeds. Among them, seed disperser species account for 42.2% of the records, pulp consumer species for 17.2%, and pulp consumer species that sporadically disperse some seeds, for 9.4% of all the species recorded.

The palmito or juçara palm (*Euterpe edulis*, Areaceae) is a dominant palm species endemic to the Atlantic forest and dependent mostly on birds for successful seed dispersal. It also occupies fragmented forest stands, remnants within the past 200 years since the establishment of extensive coffee plantations in São Paulo state (Galetti et al., 2013). Data for *E. edulis* come from (Galetti et al., 2013). Fifty-eight birds and 21 mammal species have been recorded feeding on the fruits of *E. edulis* in its distribution range. Of them, only 32 bird and six mammal species can act as legitimate seed dispersers (animals that regurgitate or defecate the seeds). The main seed dispersers are birds ranging from small thrushes (*Turdus* spp.) to large toucans (*Ramphastos* spp.). Smaller thraupids and tyrannids (e.g., *Euphonia* spp., *Tangara* spp.) feed on fruits but always drop them beneath the parent palm with no seed ingestion. Several parrot and parakeet species (e.g., *Pionus maximiliani*, *Triclaria malachitacea* and *Pyrrhura frontalis*), mid-size rodents (e.g., *Cuniculus paca* and *Dasyprocta* spp.), several species of small rodents, deer and peccaries are seed predators, and six mammals (marsupials, larger meso-mammals, tapir, etc.) are infrequent consumers of the fruits and may contribute infrequent seed dispersal events.

Sampling interactions

Frugivory events in *P. mahaleb* and *Euterpe edulis* were sampled in the field using the same protocol. We recorded all interactions between plants and frugivores (fruit consumers) for sampled trees in areas covering between 25 and 300 ha, respectively. The sampling was conducted during the fruiting seasons of *P. mahaleb* (late July to early September) and *E. edulis* (late January to mid June). We used a combination of direct observations at focal trees and feeding records during walked transects. For each interaction, we recorded the species involved, the type of interaction (active feeding and ingestion of fruit and seed, pecking pulp, crack-opening the seed, etc.), and the number of individuals involved (for details see [Jordano and Schupp, 2000](#); [Galetti et al., 2013](#)).

Sampling of direct watches at *P. mahaleb* trees totaled 190.3 and 165.0 tree-hours in two successive years (1988-1989) with additional sampling for ca. 60.0 tree-hours in 1990-1992 in four different populations. Feeding observations of frugivores at *E. edulis* were carried out during 2326 h of direct watches in ten different sites and 5-20 individual palms per site.

Combining diversified interactions into multiplex networks

We used a multiplex network approach ([De Domenico, 2022](#)) to combine the different types of interactions into a single network. The multiplex network is a type of network that consists of multiple layers, where each layer represents a different type of interaction. The multiplex network was constructed by creating

a bipartite graph for each type of interaction, where the nodes in one set represent the species involved in that interaction type (partners), and the individual trees in the population as another set; the edges represent the interactions between them (Fig. S1). Thus, a multiplex network is a specific type of multilayer network where the same set (or subset) of nodes (the trees in our case) appears in every layer, but the edges in each layer represent different types of relationships (e.g., herbivory, pollination, and seed dispersal partners in each of three layers) that taken together characterize the interactome of the trees (Jordano, P., 2024a). Thus, multiplexed networks are ideal representations for the multiple, distinct types of interactions involved in every reproductive episode of the tree population.

In multiplex networks, interlayer edges only connect corresponding nodes across layers (i.e., a tree node in one layer is connected to its counterpart representation in another layer). There are no interlayer edges between different nodes. The nodes represent the same entities across all layers. For example, a tree could be represented in multiple layers corresponding to different biotic interaction types (e.g., with its herbivory, pollination, and seed dispersal animal/fungi partners). These partner nodes in turn are just present in the layer corresponding to their interaction type. Therefore, interlayer links among repeated instances of a given tree in the three layers may indicate cumulative fitness effects derived from a layer and with effects on the subsequent layer. For example, outcomes of interactions in the pollination layer have lasting consequences for the seed dispersal layer in terms of fruit set success.

Technically, a multilayer network is a quadruple $M = (AM, EM, V, L)$

(De Domenico et al., 2014; Kivelä et al., 2014; Boccaletti et al., 2014;

De Domenico, 2022), where AM , EM and L are the nodes, links (interactions)

and layers respectively, of the M network, so that (V, EM) is a graph and $V \subset AxL$. Multilayer networks are hypergraphs, which contain multiple graphs (in our case, networks) linked to each other by interlayer links. The tensor notation is currently used to represent such multilayer structures:

$$\tau_{j,\beta}^{i,\alpha} = M_{j,\beta}^{i,\alpha}, i, j \in 1, 2, \dots, N \text{ and } \alpha, \beta \in 1, 2, 3 \text{ for } L = 1, 2, \dots, M \text{ layers.}$$

Multilayer networks can have several "aspects" in each layer (De Domenico, 2022), and an "elementary layer" is a single element in an aspect of stratification. For example, in Fig. 6, each layer is a "still photo" of interactions that actually occur over variable periods of time. Pollination interactions occur throughout the phenophase and we could imagine different variants of the L_2 layer corresponding to different months during flowering, and consider studies of the temporal dynamics of interaction networks (Olesen, JM et al., 2008) (see also Carnicer et al., 2009). Thus, each aspect of the network could contain the interactions observed in a certain time interval. Such relations are included using sequences $L = L_a d_a = 1$ of L_a sets of elementary layers, where a indexes the different aspects, d . We must take into account that $d = 0$ for a single-layer network; $d = 1$ when there is a single type of layer; and $d = 2$ when there are two types of layers. There may be different types of multilayer networks depending on whether there are links between layers and how they are arranged (see De Domenico, 2022): multiplexed or multiplexed, colored, general, etc. These configurations are very useful in ecology, where it is possible to represent variations of interaction networks in time or space (Pilosof et al., 2017; Hutchinson et al., 2019).

The current mathematical notation that allows greater precision in the analysis of multilayer networks can be found in Bollobás (1998), and De Domenico et al. (2014); De Domenico (2022). It is based on the use of successive order tensors, which allow indexing the complex multidimensional structure of multilayer

networks. Scalars (a), vectors (a_i) and matrices (A_{ij}) can be recognized by their simple tensors of rank 0, 1, and 2 respectively. Thus, an adjacency matrix for a classic network, single-layer, would have a tensor of rank 2 (two dimensions), $\tau_{ij\alpha} = a_{ij}^{[\alpha]}$, while a multilayer would have a multilayer tensor of adjacency of rank 3, $\tau_{i\beta}^{i\alpha} = M_{i\beta}^{i\alpha}$, $i, j \in 1, 2, \dots, N$ and $\alpha, \beta \in 1, 2, 3$ for $L = 3$ layers, and a multilayer with aspects, a tensor of rank 4 (e.g., [Jordano, P., 2024a](#)).

Fig. 6 considers a special type of multilayer network (a multiplex) where plant nodes are present recurrently in all layers; these in turn represent interactions with herbivores (in vegetative parts), pollinators, frugivores and post-dispersive seed predation, all of them occurring sequentially. The multiplex network, G , obviously contains multiple networks in several layers, M , with N nodes ($G = G^{[1]}, G^{[2]}, G^{[3]}, \dots, G^{[M]}$), so that each layer $\alpha = 1, 2, 3 \dots M$ contains a network $G = V, E\alpha$, with its nodes V and its set of $E\alpha$ bonds. Therefore, we will have different networks (plants by animals) for each type of interaction in each layer (Fig. S2), and networks with different types of interaction will be connected through the shared plants. That is, a representation $A = a_{[1]}, a_{[2]}, a_{[3]}, \dots, a_{[M]}$ of different adjacency matrices that contain the interactions in each layer, a_α ([Bianconi, 2021](#)). The layers are "diagonally coupled", so the links between layers occur only between shared plants (Figs. 1, 5, S3), which represents the successive effects of the mutualists and antagonists on the individual fitness of the plants. The "aspects" referred to above would represent, for example, different networks corresponding to different time intervals, such as the seasons, of each of the types of interaction: this is the case for four aspects for L1 corresponding to herbivory interactions in each of the four seasons of the year.

In Fig. 6 only one aspect has been represented for each type of interaction, which is illustrated with a network in each layer. The analysis of multilayer networks

exploits, for example, the interlayer degree correlations that exist between the degrees (degree, k) of each node in the different layers (De Domenico et al., 2014; Bianconi, 2021). The multiplex degree is not a scalar (as in a single-layer network), but is a vector: $(k_i = k^{[1]}, k^{[2]}, \dots, k^{[M]})$, whose k^α elements are the degree values in each layer. But in multiplex networks the nodes can also be connected through the layers (Fig. 6) by means of the interlayer links. For example, in Fig. 6 the individual plants are connected through links that represent the fitness effects derived from the interactions in each layer. These links between layers are called multilinks: $\vec{m} = m^{[1]}, m^{[2]}, \dots, m^{[M]}$, where the elements $m^\alpha \in 0, 1$ and are initially set to $m_\alpha = 2.0$ and later estimated with Infomap (Edler et al., 2017; Frydman et al., 2023). Therefore, multilayer networks are characterized by containing four elements (and not just two, like single-layer networks): nodes, links, multilinks and layers. In addition, nodes are divided into two groups, those that only connect with other nodes of their layer and those that have multilinks with nodes of other layers (for example, note that only individual tree nodes in Fig. S5A have multilinks). Thus in Fig. 6 only the tree nodes have multilinks. There are no multilayer solutions yet available for the analysis of bipartite networks, with which most of the analyses carried out so far refer to projections of the supra-adjacency matrix that represents all interactions in all layers, that is, in the form of matrices of added adjacency (see Frydman et al., 2023).

Table S1. List of datasets used in this study. Code, individual code for reference; Type, whether it is an individual-based (ind) or species-based network; P , number of plant species; A , number of animal species; S , total number of species; I , number of distinct pairwise interactions, C , connectance ($C = I/(A * P)$); Biome, biome type, t= tropical; nt= non-tropical; Site, specific study site. For species-based networks, species name is set to NA.

ID	Code	Type	Species	P	A	S	I	C	Biome	Reference
1	indw01	ind	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> (Anacardiaceae)	40	27	67	392	0.3630	nt	Quintero et al. 2023.
2	indw02	ind	<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i> (Anacardiaceae)	40	16	56	134	0.2094	nt	Quintero et al. 2023.
3	indw03	ind	<i>Juniperus phoenicea</i> (Cupressaceae)	35	10	45	137	0.3914	nt	Isla et al. 2023.
4	indw04	ind	<i>Juniperus phoenicea</i> (Cupressaceae)	35	10	45	154	0.4400	nt	Isla et al. 2023.
5	indw05	ind	<i>Juniperus phoenicea</i> (Cupressaceae)	35	11	46	148	0.3844	nt	Isla et al. 2023.
6	indw06	ind	<i>Lithraea molleoides</i> (Anacardiaceae)	13	10	23	37	0.2846	t	Vergara-Tabares et al. 2022.
7	indw07	ind	<i>Lithraea molleoides</i> (Anacardiaceae)	14	10	24	33	0.2357	t	Vergara-Tabares et al. 2022.
8	indw08	ind	<i>Lithraea molleoides</i> (Anacardiaceae)	14	13	27	46	0.2527	t	Vergara-Tabares et al. 2022.
9	indw09	ind	<i>Lithraea molleoides</i> (Anacardiaceae)	13	12	25	41	0.2628	t	Vergara-Tabares et al. 2022.
10	indw10	ind	<i>Lithraea molleoides</i> (Anacardiaceae)	12	11	23	29	0.2197	t	Vergara-Tabares et al. 2022.
11	indw11	ind	<i>Lithraea molleoides</i> (Anacardiaceae)	11	7	18	25	0.3247	t	Vergara-Tabares et al. 2022.
12	indw12	ind	<i>Laurus nobilis</i> (Lauraceae)	18	17	35	87	0.2843	nt	Rodríguez-Sánchez, F. 2010.
13	indw13	ind	<i>Prunus mahaleb</i> (Rosaceae)	19	20	39	211	0.5553	nt	Jordano and Schupp 2000.
14	indw14	ind	<i>Euterpe edulis</i> (Arecaceae)	17	9	26	31	0.2026	t	Friedemann et al. 2022.

ID	Code	Type	Species	P	A	S	I	C	Biome	Reference
15	indw15	ind	<i>Euterpe edulis</i> (Arecaceae)	15	7	22	25	0.2381	t	Friedemann et al. 2022
16	indw16	ind	<i>Euterpe edulis</i> (Arecaceae)	30	8	38	50	0.2083	t	Friedemann et al. 2022
17	indw17	ind	<i>Cecropia glaziovii</i> (Urticaceae)	27	37	64	124	0.1241	t	Jordano, P. 2024b
18	indw18	ind	<i>Heynea trijuga</i> (Meliaceae)	24	11	35	48	0.1818	t	Gopal et al. 2020
19	indw19	ind	<i>Myristica dactyloides</i> (Myristicaceae)	25	7	32	45	0.2571	t	Gopal et al. 2020
20	indw20	ind	<i>Persea macrantha</i> (Lauraceae)	32	21	53	186	0.2768	t	Gopal et al. 2020
21	indw21	ind	<i>Henriettea succosa</i> (Melastomataceae)	18	22	40	77	0.1944	t	Crestani et al. 2019
22	indw22	ind	<i>Prestoea decurrens</i> (Arecaceae)	31	9	40	100	0.3584	t	Lamperty et al. 2021
23	indw23	ind	<i>Corema album</i> (Ericaceae)	24	15	39	129	0.3583	nt	Villalva et al. 2024
24	indw24	ind	<i>Bursera penicillata</i> (Bursaceae)	15	11	26	43	0.2606	t	Ramaswami et al. 2017
25	indw25	ind	<i>Erythroxylum monogynum</i> (Erythroxylaceae)	12	6	18	29	0.4028	t	Ramaswami et al. 2017
26	indw26	ind	<i>Flacourtia indica</i> (Salicaceae)	13	5	18	33	0.5077	t	Ramaswami et al. 2017
27	indw27	ind	<i>Flueggea leucopyrus</i> (Phyllanthaceae)	10	8	18	22	0.2750	t	Ramaswami et al. 2017
28	indw28	ind	<i>Canthium coromandelicum</i> (Rubiaceae)	10	8	18	30	0.3750	t	Ramaswami et al. 2017
29	indw29	ind	<i>Santalum album</i> (Santalaceae)	14	10	24	38	0.2714	nt	Ramaswami et al. 2017
30	indw30	ind	<i>Ziziphus oenopolia</i> (Rhamnaceae)	15	13	28	102	0.5231	nt	Ramaswami et al. 2017
31	indw31	ind	<i>Chamaerops humilis</i> (Arecaceae)	39	6	45	76	0.3248	nt	Jácome-Flores et al. 2020
32	indw32	ind	<i>Chamaerops humilis</i> (Arecaceae)	24	6	30	57	0.3958	nt	Jácome-Flores et al. 2020

ID	Code	Type	Species	P	A	S	I	C	Biome	Reference
33	indw33	ind	<i>Miconia irwinii</i> (Melastomataceae)	15	9	24	59	0.4370	t	Guerra et al. 2017
34	indw34	ind	<i>Juniperus macrocarpa</i> (Cupressaceae)	26	11	37	72	0.2517	nt	Villalva et al. 2024
35	indw35	ind	<i>Prosopis flexuosa</i> (Fabaceae)	26	9	35	72	0.3077	nt	Miguel et al. 2018
36	indw36	ind	<i>Prosopis flexuosa</i> (Fabaceae)	28	10	38	84	0.3000	nt	Miguel et al. 2018
37	indw37	ind	<i>Prosopis flexuosa</i> (Fabaceae)	54	10	64	112	0.2074	nt	Miguel et al. 2018
38	indw38	ind	<i>Prosopis flexuosa</i> (Fabaceae)	35	8	43	61	0.2179	nt	Miguel et al. 2018
39	indw39	ind	<i>Prosopis flexuosa</i> (Fabaceae)	29	9	38	99	0.3793	nt	Miguel et al. 2018
40	indw40	ind	<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i> (Anacardiaceae)	26	16	42	93	0.2236	t	Visso et al. 2022
41	indw41	ind	<i>Phillyrea angustifolia</i> (Oleaceae)	10	16	26	72	0.4500	nt	Moracho, E et al. 2025
42	indw42	ind	<i>Phillyrea angustifolia</i> (Oleaceae)	9	12	21	41	0.3796	nt	Moracho, E et al. 2025
43	indw43	ind	<i>Marcgravia longifolia</i> (Marcgraviaceae)	24	43	67	127	0.1231	t	Thiel et al. 2024
44	indw44	ind	<i>Osyris lanceolata</i> (Santalaceae)	19	14	33	62	0.2331	nt	Moracho, E et al. 2025
45	indw45	ind	<i>Narungi crenulata</i> (Rutaceae)	22	12	34	62	0.2348	t	Jayanth et al. 2024
46	indw46	ind	<i>Ziziphus oenopolia</i> (Rhamnaceae)	20	13	33	57	0.2192	nt	Jayanth et al. 2024
47	sdw00	sp	NA	77	68	145	203	0.0388	nt	Jordano, P. 2007
48	sdw01	sp	NA	25	36	61	253	0.2811	nt	Moracho, E et al. 2025
54	sdw02	sp	NA	29	78	107	479	0.2118	nt	Moracho, E et al. 2025
50	sdw02a	sp	NA	16	44	60	201	0.2855	nt	Quintero et al. 2022

ID	Code	Type	Species	P	A	S	I	C	Biome	Reference
51	sdw02b	sp	NA	13	23	36	86	0.2876	nt	Moracho, E et al. 2025
52	sdw02c	sp	NA	6	9	15	19	0.3519	nt	Moracho, E et al. 2025
53	sdw02d	sp	NA	6	18	24	27	0.2500	nt	Moracho, E et al. 2025
54	sdw03	sp	NA	17	29	46	147	0.2982	nt	García-Castaño 2011
55	sdw04	sp	NA	3	6	9	11	0.6111	nt	Jordano 1993a
56	sdw05	sp	NA	5	6	11	17	0.5667	nt	Jordano 1993a
57	sdw06	sp	NA	5	6	11	18	0.6000	nt	Jordano 1993a
58	sdw07	sp	NA	9	6	15	36	0.6667	nt	Jordano 1993a
59	sdb19	sp	NA	25	61	86	536	0.3515	t	Lambert 1989
60	sdb20	sp	NA	207	110	317	1329	0.0584	t	Silva et al. 2002
61	sdb21	sp	NA	171	40	211	877	0.1282	t	Wheelwright et al. 1984
62	sdw08	sp	NA	31	9	40	119	0.4265	t	Beehler 1983
63	sdw09	sp	NA	7	6	13	29	0.6905	nt	Sorensen 1981
64	sdw10	sp	NA	16	10	26	126	0.7875	t	Frost 1988
65	sdw11	sp	NA	12	7	19	52	0.6190	nt	Guitian 1983
66	sdw12	sp	NA	35	29	64	181	0.1783	t	Galetti and Pizo 1996
67	sdw13	sp	NA	5	27	32	91	0.6741	t	Kantak 1981
68	sdw14	sp	NA	11	14	25	47	0.3052	nt	Snow and Snow 1988

ID	Code	Type	Species	P	A	S	I	C	Biome	Reference
69	sdb15	sp	NA	17	8	26	84	0.6176	t	Tutin et al. 1997.
70	sdw16	sp	NA	27	8	35	65	0.3009	nt	Noma and Yumoto 1997.
71	sdw17	sp	NA	71	7	79	214	0.4306	t	Crome 1975.
72	sdw18	sp	NA	50	14	64	284	0.4057	t	Snow and Snow 1971.
73	sdw22	sp	NA	7	21	28	57	0.3878	nt	Baird 1980.
74	sdw23	sp	NA	41	5	46	89	0.4341	t	Innis 1989.
75	sdw24	sp	NA	15	49	64	158	0.2150	t	Pizo 2004.
76	sdw25	sp	NA	22	13	35	123	0.4301	t	Fritth et al. 1976.
77	sdb26	sp	NA	45	46	91	318	0.1536	t	Donatti et al. 2011.
78	sdb27	sp	NA	314	132	446	1902	0.0459	t	Fuzessy et al. 2022.
79	sdw28	sp	NA	33	88	121	452	0.1556	t	Schleuning et al. 2011a.
80	sdw29	sp	NA	49	16	65	180	0.2296	t	Castro 2007.
81	sdw30	sp	NA	13	45	58	196	0.3350	t	Correia 1997.
82	sdw31	sp	NA	13	30	43	158	0.4051	t	Alves 2008.
83	sdw32	sp	NA	9	30	39	101	0.3741	t	Athie 2009.
84	sdw33	sp	NA	25	28	53	115	0.1643	t	Ferreira Fadini and De Marco J
85	sdw34	sp	NA	26	22	48	105	0.1836	t	Hasui 1994.
86	sdw35	sp	NA	22	20	42	89	0.2023	t	Silva 2011.

ID	Code	Type	Species	P	A	S	I	C	Biome	Reference
87	sdw36-1	sp	NA	12	15	27	44	0.2444	t	da Silva et al. 2015.
88	sdw36-2	sp	NA	23	29	52	152	0.2279	t	da Silva et al. 2015.
89	sdw36-3	sp	NA	14	14	28	49	0.2500	t	da Silva et al. 2015.
90	sdw37	sp	NA	6	28	34	56	0.3333	t	Robinson 2015.
91	sdw38	sp	NA	30	58	88	270	0.1552	t	Rodrigues 2015.
92	sdw39	sp	NA	18	9	27	138	0.8519	nt	Burns 2013.
93	sdw40	sp	NA	8	12	20	46	0.4792	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
94	sdw40	sp	NA	7	11	18	39	0.5065	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
95	sdw40	sp	NA	9	13	22	51	0.4359	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
96	sdw40	sp	NA	8	13	21	44	0.4231	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
97	sdw40	sp	NA	8	10	18	37	0.4625	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
98	sdw40	sp	NA	8	10	18	38	0.4750	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
99	sdw40	sp	NA	8	11	19	41	0.4659	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
100	sdw40	sp	NA	10	13	23	52	0.4000	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
101	sdw40	sp	NA	8	15	23	65	0.5417	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
102	sdw40	sp	NA	9	16	25	50	0.3472	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
103	sdw40	sp	NA	6	20	26	49	0.4083	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.
104	sdw40	sp	NA	8	19	27	64	0.4211	nt	Albrecht et al. 2015.

ID	Code	Type	Species	P	A	S	I	C	Biome	Reference
105	sdw41	sp	NA	22	17	39	100	0.2674	nt	Andrade et al. 2011.
106	sdw42	sp	NA	6	7	13	29	0.6905	t	Carlo et al. 2003.
107	sdw43	sp	NA	34	20	54	129	0.1897	t	Yang et al. 2013.
108	sdw44	sp	NA	14	6	20	36	0.4286	t	Garcia et al. 2000.
109	sdw45	sp	NA	81	18	99	282	0.1934	t	Gorchov et al. 1995.
110	sdw46	sp	NA	35	14	49	130	0.2653	t	Palmeirim et al. 1989.
111	sdw47	sp	NA	35	14	49	154	0.3143	t	Lopez and Vaughan 2004.
112	sdw48	sp	NA	43	15	58	140	0.2171	t	Heleno et al. 2013.
113	sdw49	sp	NA	22	7	29	69	0.4481	t	Hernandez-Montero et al. 2015.
114	sdw49	sp	NA	19	6	25	53	0.4649	t	Hernandez-Montero et al. 2015.
115	sdw50	sp	NA	24	7	31	74	0.4405	t	Passos et al. 2003.
116	sdw51	sp	NA	13	7	20	43	0.4725	t	Pedro 1992.
117	sdw52	sp	NA	17	20	37	103	0.3029	t	Poulin et al. 1999.
118	sdw53	sp	NA	56	20	76	160	0.1429	t	Sarmento et al. 2014.
119	sdw54	sp	NA	30	31	61	219	0.2355	nt	Stiebel and Bairlein 2008a,b.
120	sdw55	sp	NA	7	6	13	29	0.6905	t	Silveira 2006.
121	sdw57	sp	NA	36	41	77	163	0.1104	t	Saavedra et al. 2014.
122	sdw57	sp	NA	20	23	43	72	0.1565	t	Saavedra et al. 2014.

ID	Code	Type	Species	P	A	S	I	C	Biome	Reference
123	sdw58	sp	NA	8	30	38	77	0.3208	nt	Menke et al. 2012.
124	sdw58	sp	NA	7	38	45	111	0.4173	nt	Menke et al. 2012.
125	sdw58	sp	NA	8	34	42	96	0.3529	nt	Menke et al. 2012.
126	sdw58	sp	NA	8	39	47	123	0.3942	nt	Menke et al. 2012.
127	sdw59	sp	NA	13	7	20	42	0.4615	t	Hayashi 1996.
128	sdw60	sp	NA	17	26	43	79	0.1787	nt	Costa et al. 2014.
129	sdw61	sp	NA	21	35	56	186	0.2531	t	Giannini and Kalko 2004.
130	sdb62	sp	NA	787	343	1130	8320	0.0308	t	Bello et al. 2017.
131	sdb63	sp	NA	73	39	112	285	0.1001	t	Bello et al. 2017.
133	sdb64	sp	NA	47	42	89	163	0.0826	t	Bello et al. 2017.
134	sdb65	sp	NA	203	107	310	1124	0.0517	t	Bello et al. 2017.
135	sdb66	sp	NA	14	22	36	70	0.2273	t	Kindel 1996.
136	sdw67	sp	NA	73	128	201	826	0.0884	t	Stevenson et al. 2015.
137	sdw68	sp	NA	14	42	56	119	0.2024	t	Walther et al. 2018.
138	sdb69	sp	NA	60	75	135	780	0.1733	t	Palacio et al. 2016.
139	sdw70	sp	NA	90	68	158	586	0.0958	t	Machado-de Souza et al. 2019.
140	sdw71	sp	NA	43	47	90	355	0.1757	t	Naniwadekar et al. 2019.
141	sdw72-1	sp	NA	140	98	238	572	0.0417	nt	Schlautmann et al. 2021.

ID	Code	Type	Species	P	A	S	I	C	Biome	Reference
142	sdw72-2	sp	NA	7	14	21	25	0.2551	nt	Schlautmann et al. 2021.
143	sdw72-3	sp	NA	230	147	377	1419	0.0420	nt	Schlautmann et al. 2021.
144	sdw72-4	sp	NA	19	8	27	45	0.2961	nt	Schlautmann et al. 2021.
145	sdw72-5	sp	NA	153	133	286	795	0.0391	nt	Schlautmann et al. 2021.
146	sdw72-6	sp	NA	236	150	386	1543	0.0436	nt	Schlautmann et al. 2021.
147	sdw72-7	sp	NA	361	226	587	2398	0.0294	nt	Schlautmann et al. 2021.
148	sdw72-8	sp	NA	74	53	127	244	0.0622	nt	Schlautmann et al. 2021.
149	sdw72-9	sp	NA	90	65	155	408	0.0697	nt	Schlautmann et al. 2021.
150	sdw73	sp	NA	44	42	86	260	0.1407	nt	Ramos-Robles et al. 2016.
151	sdw74	sp	NA	88	33	121	507	0.1746	t	Schleuning et al. 2011b.
152	sdw75	sp	NA	22	45	67	116	0.1172	t	Dehling et al. 2021.
153	sdw76	sp	NA	26	39	65	122	0.1203	t	Dehling et al. 2021.
154	sdw77	sp	NA	26	51	77	125	0.0943	t	Dehling et al. 2021.
155	sdw78	sp	NA	20	36	56	79	0.1097	t	Dehling et al. 2021.
156	sdw79	sp	NA	52	61	113	394	0.1242	t	Dehling et al. 2021.
157	sdw80	sp	NA	26	51	77	207	0.1561	t	Dehling et al. 2021.
158	sdw81	sp	NA	22	19	41	50	0.1196	t	Dehling et al. 2021.
159	sdw82	sp	NA	27	24	51	106	0.1636	t	Dehling et al. 2021.

ID	Code	Type	Species	<i>P</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>C</i>	Biome	Reference
160	sdw83	sp	NA	12	17	29	56	0.2745	nt	Dehling et al. 2021.
161	sdw84	sp	NA	13	22	35	54	0.1888	nt	Dehling et al. 2021.
162	sdw85	sp	NA	14	25	39	55	0.1571	nt	Plein et al. 2013.
163	sdw86	sp	NA	13	24	37	67	0.2147	nt	Plein et al. 2013.
164	sdw87	sp	NA	18	26	44	73	0.1560	nt	Plein et al. 2013.

Figures

Figure 1: Correlation matrices among variables used to characterize functional diversity, *FD*. Numbers indicate the Pearson product-moment correlations between each pair of variables, with color tone proportional to the correlation value. Shown are results for the two frugivore assemblages studied: *Prunus mahaleb* (Jordano and Schupp, 2000) and *Euterpe edulis* (Galetti et al., 2013).

Figure 2: Monolayer networks of *Prunus mahaleb* tree interactions with different partners. A. Herbivory and fungi, B. Pollination, C. Seed dispersal. The width of links is proportional to the frequency of interactions between each tree and its partner taxa. Node type: yellow triangles, individual taxa; blue dots, animal and fungi taxa.

Figure 3: Supra-adjacency matrix of frugivore-plant interactions. The square matrix shows the number of interactions between each pair of tree (numeric labels) and animal/fungi species (scientific names). The matrix is symmetric and has the interlayer links highlighted (set to the same value to improve visualization). The color intensity is proportional to the frequency of interactions, with darker colors representing more interactions. Red brackets highlight the adjacency matrices of each layer, along with their respective symmetric around the major diagonal of the supra-adjacency matrix.

Figure 4: Patterns of multilayer strength (top) and multilayer centrality (bottom) for the individual *Prunus mahaleb* trees studied. The trees are ranked by their strength (top) and centrality (bottom) values in the multilayer network. Bar color indicates the type of interaction: dark blue, the whole multilayer network; lighter blue tones identify the three monolayers studied (herbivory, pollination, and seed dispersal) with decreasing blue tone.

Figure 5: Covariation patterns between centrality (top) and strength (bottom) values for all the nodes in the network; for each node (blue dot) axes represent the values on the monolayer and the multilayer network.

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